

PLANTING NEAR MOUNT HOOD

A typical scene in the Oregon National Forest at the Still Creek Planting Station, showing the ground which has been devastated by fire and which is being planted with young seedling conifers. The rehabilitation of such areas as this means a sure and safe water supply and future timber, as well as picturesque scenery. (Frontispiece.)

CHOOSING THE BEST TREE SEEDS

The Influence of Parental Character and Environment upon the Progeny of Douglas Fir—Study Will Extend Over at Least Forty Years

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THE influence of the character of the parent plant upon the development of the progeny of that plant is a matter of vital importance in plant culture. The influence of the parental habitat as reflected in the seed productivity and seed quality is likewise important, for practical and economic reasons. That both these considerations are regarded in ordinary agriculture is a matter of common knowledge; but it is not so commonly known that the application of the principles of genetics to the culture of forest trees and to the practical management of forest lands has come to be a necessity of modern forestry.

In the Forest Service this application is required in seed collection for extensive artificial reforestation, and in the choosing of seed trees to be left in logging operations in the National Forests. In reforestation work, great quantities of forest tree seeds are used annually by the government nurseries, and this seed must be harvested within a very short time in the fall. The bulk of it is collected by the Forest Service itself, but much of it must often be purchased from commercial seedsmen. In the past there was no experience in American forestry to serve as a guide in this matter, and the gathering of the seed was therefore controlled by expediency rather than by the principles of genetics. Since large quantities were required quickly, it was natural to collect such seed as was nearest and easiest to obtain. There is good reason for believing that in America, as in Europe, there resulted from this cause occasional fundamental errors in planting, as, for example, the planting in severe sites at high altitudes of plants raised from seed collected on

moderate sites at low altitudes. In Europe, particularly in Sweden, the percentage of failures in such plantations was often excessively high, and the failure frequently did not occur until the plantations had reached the age of ten or fifteen years. Guided by that experience, much good can be done in this country by the appropriate disposition of seed the source of which is definitely known. But before it is possible to specify with certainty what sort of seed is best for any particular set of conditions, it is necessary to know something of the influence of the character and environment of the parent tree upon the qualities most desired in its progeny.

EUROPEAN STUDIES

A vast amount of work has been done upon this same problem with European species by the forest experiment stations of Europe. For over twenty years the subject has received the attention of such eminent students as Mayr, Cieslar, Engler, Zederbauer and Huffel. Some work has been undertaken with Douglas fir, from seed obtained through the Forest Service, by Count von Berg, of Livonia, Russia. The work of Professor Engler of Switzerland has been especially exhaustive and productive of practical results with Austrian pine. General principles have been evolved which have been applied, in a measure, to American practice. But for any species of such extensive range and large value as Douglas fir, the only satisfactory procedure is to conduct an individual study for the species, which answers by experimental results the questions which can only be so answered.

The study here described, known as

¹ Mr. Kraebel is now with the 10th Engineers (Forest) in France, and was hence unable to read proof on his article.

GIANT DOUGLAS FIR OF CALIFORNIA

More than eight feet in diameter, the magnificent Douglas fir standing to the immediate right of the track is the type of tree with which tree growers are gradually reforesting the devastated areas. (Fig. 1.)

the Douglas Fir Seed Study, was initiated in the fall of 1912 at the Wind River Experiment Station near Carson, Washington. It will be continued for forty years, or as much longer as it will yield data of value. The data gathered during the first few years are expected to serve primarily as a guide in the collection of seed, and secondarily as an aid in the selection of seed trees to be left standing in timber-sale cuttings. Among the immediate questions to be answered are the following:

1. What class of tree produces the best quality and quantity of seed— young, middle-aged or old; healthy or diseased?

2. What particular qualities of seed are required to produce the most desirable seedlings for artificial reforestation on various sites?

3. What is the influence of locality of the parent tree upon the progeny raised from that tree?

It will be appreciated at once that there are innumerable questions, subordinate to these, which enter the problem but which cannot be discussed in the brief compass of this article.

METHODS

In the fall of 1912, cones were collected from 127 different trees in ten different localities on the west slope of the Cascade Mountains from northern Washington to midwestern Oregon. The classes of trees from which cones were gathered are as follows:

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|---|--|---------------------------|
| 1. (a) Very young (14-30 years) | } Open-grown trees at
low altitudes. | |
| (b) 75-100 years old | | |
| (c) 100-200 years old | | |
| (d) Old (over 300 years) | | |
| 2. (a) Second growth (60, 65 and 100 years) | } Dense-grown trees at
low altitudes. | |
| (b) Old growth (220 and 600 years) | | |
| 3. (a) Second growth | } Trees at high altitudes. | |
| (b) Old growth | | |
| 4. (a) Young (40 years) | } Trees from | } Effect of poor
soil. |
| (b) Old (150 years) | | |
| 5. (a) Diseased | } Trees of middle age (275-400 years). | |
| (b) Sound | | |

The altitudes of the sites varied from 100 to 3,850 feet above sea-level. The trees ranged in age from fourteen years to 600 years, and, in size, from a diam-

eter of 3½ inches to 6½ feet. The trees were carefully chosen for the desired qualities, and for each condition several trees were used in order to minimize the likelihood of disturbance through the possible erratic qualities of some individual tree. By this means a group of four to ten trees, rather than a single tree, became the unit of the study. The cones were taken from all parts of the crown of each tree and the proportion of those taken to the total yield of the tree was carefully noted. For each tree a detailed description was made by the collector, including such points as size, age, tree class (whether dominant or suppressed in the stand) character of crown, condition of health, etc., besides the important features of the site in which the tree grew. A sketch of the tree was also made to show the shape and proportions of the crown and the location of cones upon it. The trees were not marked for future examination, since, in the case of the older trees, the cones were gathered after the trees had been felled in the process of logging.

As the cones were received at the Experiment Station each lot was given a number, and all information concerning the seed or seedling resulting from that lot of cones has thenceforward been recorded under this number. By this means the chance of personal prejudice toward one conclusion or another in making observations is eliminated, for the observer knows nothing of the source of the stock he is examining. From the

time of their arrival at the Experiment Station, the cones and seeds, and the seedlings raised from them, have had identical treatment. In a number of

THRESHING DOUGLAS FIR CONES

When facilities do not permit sending the entire cones in to the kiln house, the ranger threshes the cones where they are collected, thus leaving only the seed to be sent to the main station. Although not so advantageous in many ways, this method allows large quantities of seeds to be brought from the outposts which would not otherwise be available. (Fig. 2.)

cases larger quantities of cones than the usual sample were collected from particular trees for use in special supplementary studies. The various steps in the study have yielded voluminous data on the cones, seeds and seedlings, only the general nature of which can be indicated here.

THE CONE AND SEED

1. Study of the green, unopened cones, their condition and color; measurements to obtain the "number of cones per bushel" and "number of bushels per tree."

2. Drying of the cones; extraction and cleaning of the seed. Records were made of the amount of uncleaned and

cleaned seed per sample, per tree and per bushel of cones.

3. Seed study. Counts, weights and measurements to determine size of seed; number of seed (with chaff, mill-cleaned and hand-cleaned) per pound and per bushel of cones; cutting tests to determine purity.

4. Germination. Tests made in the greenhouse during the winter of 1912 were unsatisfactory. A sample of 300 seeds from each lot was therefore sown in the nursery in the spring of 1913 for outdoor germination, and this proved perfectly reliable. Such a test has been made each spring since 1913, and will be repeated annually so long as there remains sufficient seed in any of the

original lots. Uniform storage conditions have been maintained from the beginning.

THE SEEDLING

For the purposes of this study it is the behavior of the seedling in the nursery, and more especially its behavior as a growing tree in its ultimate place in the planting site, which forms the basis of final judgment upon the desirability of that seedling. In order to secure material for the study of this behavior, the seedlings of 1913 and 1914 were observed for two years in the nursery and then out-planted on various sites to form permanent forest stands.

Series of 1913.—The seedlings resulting from the germination tests of 1913 were closely watched in the fall of that year to determine the time of winter bud formation or "hardening." In the spring of 1914 they were transplanted in the nursery and at that time a number of seedlings was taken at random from each lot for minute study and comparison. In the fall of 1914 the height growth was recorded by measuring every tenth plant in the beds, and the process of "hardening" was again observed.

In the spring of 1915 the plants, then two years old, were lifted for final planting in six different sites in four different geographical regions. Ten representative plants of each lot were again taken for intensive laboratory study. Twenty plants of each lot were sent to each of these sites, making a total final planting of 120 trees for each original seed tree from which cones were gathered. For twelve of the original trees, possessing features for which broader averages were desired, from 50 to 100 transplants were set out in each site. The plants were spaced 7 feet apart each way. Each plantation covers an area of nearly four acres and contains approximately 3,400 pedigreed plants, each of which is marked with an aluminum tag bearing the original parent tree number and the individual number of the seedling in its row. The total number of plants of the

1913 series, outplanted in 1915, is thus 20,400.

Series of 1914.—In order to strengthen the whole study, the entire procedure outlined above was repeated with the seedlings of the 1914 germination series, each operation following the similar operation in the 1913 series by just one year. In the final outplanting to the same sites in 1916, however, only ten plants for each parent tree were set out in each site, since it was believed that this number was sufficient to serve as a check upon the 1915 plants.

PLANTING SITES

The permanent planting areas, and the features for which they were selected are as follows:

1. Northern Cascades: On the Snoqualmie National Forest; 40 miles east of Everett, Washington, on the South Fork of the Stillaguamish River; altitude, 1,900 feet.

2. Middle Cascades: On the Columbia Forest; 7 miles north of the Columbia River; altitude, 1,200 feet.

3. Middle Cascades for altitudinal range: Three areas on the Oregon Forest; 5 miles southwest of Mt. Hood, on the headwaters of the Sandy River:

I. 2,800 feet elevation, north slope.

II. 3,700 feet elevation, north slope.

III. 4,600 feet elevation, north slope.

4. Coast Region: On the Siuslaw Forest, in the coast range (Mt. Hebo); 20 miles south of Tillamook; altitude, 2,000 feet.

RESULTS

The results of the study fall naturally into two divisions, the first including the statistical data concerning the cones, the seed, and the germination and behavior of seedlings in the nursery; the second embracing the development of the seedlings in the final field plantations.

The results of that portion of the study dealing with the cones, the seed, and the seedling in the nursery have been exhaustively presented in a progress report written in 1914 by C. P. Willis.² The great range of conditions

² For the substance of this official report the reader is referred to the article, "A Study of Douglas Fir Seed," by C. P. Willis and J. V. Hofmann, in the Proceedings of the Society of American Foresters, Vol. x (1915), pp. 141-164.

DUMPING DRIED CONES INTO ELEVATOR

After the cones are collected, they are brought to the kiln house where they are placed on trays and put in hoppers which carry them to the shaker, where the seeds are removed. (Fig. 3.)

represented by the parent trees made possible so large a number of comparisons and factor combinations that eighty-three tables were compiled to express graphically the numerous relationships. The interplay of the factors involved can be indicated by listing them in juxtaposition:

Age of the parent tree.	}
Size of the parent tree.	
Health of the parent tree.	
Growing space of the parent tree.	
Altitude of the parent tree.	
Latitude of the parent tree	
Soil quality of the site.	

Seed:

- (a) Yield of cones per tree.
- (b) Size of cones.
- (c) Yield of seed per tree.
- (d) Size of seed.
- (e) Quality of seed, germination per cent.

Seedling in nursery:

- (a) Establishment.
- (b) Size of seedling.
- (c) Rate of growth.
- (d) Hardiness.

It will be appreciated that not all the first column factors will affect all the points in the second column, and also that such a feature as "size of seed" might influence both "establishment" and "size of seedling" in its own column. It is not possible, within the limits of the present article, to discuss the detailed conclusions, but some idea of their trend can be given by a consideration of their practical application. The tabular comparisons were variously decisive, but, on the whole, the results have served to formulate a number of recommendations for cone collection and for the selection of seed trees. These recommendations are not regarded as final, for it is almost certain that the future development of the plantations will change some of our present ideas. European experience has shown that such long-lived plants as forest trees require some years to reveal their hereditary traits. In Sweden, for example, the failure of many plantations from imported seed did not become evident until twelve or fifteen years after planting. The following recommendations are based upon two years' study of seedlings in the nursery. It seems inevitable, therefore, that the observation, through many years, of the same seedlings in various field plantations must result in some reversal of opinion and in the disclosure of facts at present unthought of.

1. Gather cones in a locality as cold as or colder than the planting site. The colder the habitat of the parent, the stronger is the tendency of the seedling toward early maturing of growth.

2. Collect from open-grown trees where practicable, since such trees produce larger crops of cones, larger yields

of good seed per bushel of cones, and larger two-year-old seedlings than do forest-grown trees.

3. Seek large cones where practicable. Large cones have large seeds which offer better chance of seedling establishment and produce large first-year seedlings. (This advantage of size is usually lost in the second year.)

4. Collect from young or middle-aged, small or large trees, as convenience demands. Young trees produce large seed and vigorous seedlings; such trees are easy to climb and permit rapid work in collecting.

5. Avoid trees growing on poor soil. Such trees give low yield of good seed per bushel of cones. Seedlings also seem to inherit a stuntedness of growth.

6. Avoid extremely high altitudes in collecting unless the ultimate planting site is very high. High altitude trees generally give small yield of good seed per bushel of cones.

7. Avoid trees diseased by fungous growth, "conky" trees, for these give low yield of good seed, and the seedlings are inclined to be stunted. Until this point is cleared by further study, it is safest to assume that the tendency to disease, or rather the lack of resistance to disease, is hereditary.

8. Avoid insect-infested cones because of small amount of good seed. Insects work rapidly and the damage is worse if the cone crop is light for the locality

GENERAL VIEW OF SEED KILN

Located at Wyeth, Oregon, the Wyeth Seed Kiln is typical of the type of plant where the Douglas fir seeds are prepared for germination. (Fig. 4.)

because the insect attack is then concentrated.

SELECTING TIMBER SALE SEED TREES

With the exception of the factors of soil quality and health of the tree, all considerations in this matter can be subordinated to commercial expediency. Since every tree left on a cutting reduces the lumber yield of the area to the extent of its own merchantable volume, it is essential to leave as few trees as are necessary to assure the reforestation of the area. The best seed tree, therefore, from the lumberman's standpoint, would be one which is worthless for lumber, hence a tree which is either defective or below merchantable size.

From the standpoint of the silviculturist, the best tree to leave would be the one which produces the greatest quantity of good seed per tree. The present study indicates that medium-aged (200-300 years), rather large trees (3 to 4 feet in diameter) produce five times as much good seed as very small young trees or very old large trees. Unfortunately, such trees are also the most

valuable for lumber and consequently the most costly to leave.

Young or old trees can be left as seed trees, but the number left should be guided by the amount of seed produced as just stated.

Open-grown trees should be preferred. These yield more seed and better seedlings, and are also more windfirm than forest-grown trees.

Avoid, if practicable, leaving trees which grow on local patches of poor soil. These yield less seed and smaller seedlings than trees on good soil.

Avoid leaving diseased trees. These produce less good seed and smaller seedlings than sound trees, other things being equal. There is also a possibility that the progeny of such trees will be of low vigor in resisting disease.

Regarding the last rule little can be declared with certainty. Whether the tendency to disease is inherited; whether this tendency, if inherited, is offset by giving the offspring the advantage of a more favorable environment; and whether we actually lower the quality of the forest by leaving diseased seed trees—

SEED BED FRAMES MEAN SAFETY FOR SEEDLINGS

Frames are constructed with burlap sides and shaded tops which insure even germination. Covered with wire netting, rodents and birds are unable to gain entrance. Care and attention paid to seedlings assures a sturdy growth for transplanting. (Fig. 5.)

these questions constitute a problem of vital importance and absorbing interest. It is not possible to draw positive conclusions from three or four years of work. It is hoped that the future development, on the different planting sites, of the seedlings from diseased parent trees will throw some light upon this problem. It is planned, moreover, to amplify this phase of the study by the collection of seed in the fall of 1917 from a considerable number of diseased trees, and from an equal number of trees which are sound but otherwise as similar as possible to the diseased trees. The pathology of the diseased trees will be carefully studied and the whole conduct of the work will be more intensive than was the case for this particular phase of the present study.

RESULTS FROM FIELD PLANTATIONS

The compilations of the growth measurements for two years in the 1915 plantations and for one year in the 1916

plantations have served only to emphasize the impossibility of drawing conclusions from such short-time observations. There were no consistencies which can be cited as even indicating the possible trend of differences among the various classes of trees. It is too soon to expect the true hereditary qualities of the trees to appear in any measurable degree. At the end of the first five years, however, detailed compilations will be made which are expected to yield at least indicative results. At the end of twenty years the problem, for immediate practical purposes, should be solved.

It is a superior merit of Government research that the element of time need not hamper the plan or ultimate conduct of an important study. In the present instance it is planned to make observations of the field plantations for at least forty years, and in all likelihood it will be found that valuable data can be ac-

accumulated through one entire "management rotation." Such a rotation will probably mean, for Douglas fir, a period of 120 or 150 years. The imagination refuses to venture concerning the methods of study at so distant a time. The largeness of the idea is at once gratifying and disturbing, for one feels both the importance of the work and the responsibility of doing rightly the early steps in that work, lest the initial errors and omissions grow in magnitude with the advancing years.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The plan for the seed collecting and seed testing of the Douglas Fir Seed Study was prepared in 1912 by Thornton T. Munger, then Forest Assistant at Portland, Oregon. The conduct of the seed collection and all of the first year's work was under the direction of C. P. Willis, of the Wind River Experiment Station. His careful work with the cones and seeds was productive of the detailed conclusions upon that phase of the study. He has also prepared a report on numerous incidental studies relative to methods of cone drying, seed extraction and time of cone gathering. Since 1913 J. V. Hofmann has been Director of the Experiment Station and has had general supervision of the work. He planned the field plantations and selected the sites for the altitudinal and regional tests for hardiness and growth of seedlings. The writer's connection with the study began with the collection of a portion of the cones, and has continued to the present time. The article by Mr. Willis and Dr. Hofmann in the *Proceedings* has been freely drawn upon in the present writing.

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7. Annual Reports of the American Breeder's Association, Washington, D. C. These reports contain valuable reports and reviews by the Committee on Breeding Nut and Forest Trees, many of which are pertinent to the present work.

8. The work of a number of European investigators may be found as follows:

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Dr. Dengler: *Zeitschrift für Forst und Jagdwesen*, 1903, p. 137.

Prof. G. Huffel: *Revue des Eaux et Forêts*, 1912.

Dr. M. Kienitz: *Zeitschrift für Forst und Jagdwesen*, 1911, p. 4.

Cooperative Move to Improve California Citrus Orchards

Six years of study have proved that more than 25% of the trees in California citrus orchards are unprofitable. They are undesirable bud variations that bear little or nothing. The California Fruit Growers' Exchange has now established a department of bud selec-

tion, the object of which will be to secure and furnish to all growers buds from tested trees, in order that they may propagate only desirable strains of oranges. This is a unique instance of widespread application of the teaching of modern plant-breeding.